

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods

Maintainers for WA cytoplasmic male sterility

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PR108, released in the Punjab for general cultivation in 1986, has been found to be a maintainer for WA cytoplasmic male sterility from V20 A/PR 108. PR106-1, a secondary selection from popular high-yielding variety PR106, exhibited F₁ sterility in the cross V20 A/PR 106-1. Three backcrosses of these lines have

Characteristics of 3 maintainer lines. Kapurthala, India.

Cytoplasm source	Maintainer line	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)
V20 A (WA)	PR108	7.0	142	104	180
PMS3 A (WA)	HKR126	7.1	144	105	140
V20 A (WA)	PR106-1	6.9	144	100	175
	PR106 (check)	6.9	144	100	172
	LSD (0.05)	0.7	—	—	36

^a Av of 3 replications over 4 locations.

been added to WA cytoplasm. The progeny of each backcross was totally sterile, with no stained pollen grains.

Another promising line, HKR 126, also acted as maintainer for WA cytoplasmic male sterility and is in the pipeline for

conversion into a CMS version by recurrent backcrossing/nucleus substitution method. The main features of the three new CMS lines are compared with those of PR106 (most popular rice variety) in the table. ■

Influence of syringomycin on differentiation of androgenic cultures in rice

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We investigated the influence of different concentrations of syringomycin isolated from *Pseudomonas syringae* on the regeneration of calli obtained by anther culture from dihaploid rice cultivar Mariana.

Anthers were excised and placed on N6 medium supplemented with 2 mg

Rhizogenesis and regeneration of rice anther calli with 3 levels of syringomycin.

Parameter	Control	10 ppm	20 ppm	30 ppm
Calli set (no.)	108	111	113	114
Calli (no.) with rhizogenesis	12	18	17	46
Green regenerants (no.)	1	2	2	13
Albino regenerants (no.)	1	2	3	20

2.4-D/liter for callus induction. Toxin was added at 10, 20, and 30 active units in ml active ingredient/ml in the MS regeneration medium (without other stimulators). For control, no toxin was added. pH of the test variants was reduced to 5.6.

Calli measuring 2-3 mm were transferred to the regeneration medium. After

20 d at 26-28°C, calli were transferred to a fresh nutritive medium.

Rhizogenesis and regeneration were measured before and after appearance of plantlets. Syringomycin stimulated rhizogenesis and plant regeneration (see table). Resistance in the dihaploid lines obtained is being field-tested. ■

Seed set on different rice CMS lines

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We compared seed set on different cytoplasmically male sterile (CMS) lines during 1989 wet season. Ten (PMS1 to 10) CMS (A) and their maintainer (B) lines were transplanted in 6.2- × 4.0-m plots with four replications. Row ratio was 2 female: 1 male.

Each plot had 10 pairs of female rows and 11 male rows at 20- × 20-cm plant spacing. Row direction was perpendicular to the prevailing wind direction during anthesis. The CMS lines were allowed to be naturally pollinated by the B lines.

Twenty panicles were taken at random from the center five pairs of rows of the female lines and seed set calculated as number of filled spikelets divided by total number of spikelets.

Seed set ranged from 7.4% in PMS7 A to 18.5% in PMS10 A (see table). ■

Seed set on different A lines. Kapurthala, India.

PMS line	Seed set (%)	Days to 50% flowering	
		A line	B line
PMS1	12.7	105	101
PMS2	8.2	105	101
PMS3	13.3	105	100
PMS4	11.8	106	102
PMS5	9.2	106	102
PMS6	9.4	106	102
PMS7	7.4	105	101
PMS8	14.6	104	100
PMS9	17.2	101	97
PMS10	18.5	104	100
LSD			
	0.05	1.4	
	0.01	1.9	